

Research Article**Comparison between Tolteridine and Solifenacin in cases of Urinary Incontinence in term of side effects**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To compare Tolteridine and Solifenacin in cases of Urinary Incontinence in term of side effects.

Material and methods: This randomized controlled trial was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology THQ Hospital, Sadiqabad from March 2017 to September 2017. Comparison between Tolteridine and Solifenacin in cases of Urinary Incontinence in term of side effects was done.

Results: Mean age of patients was 58.34±12.54 years. Dry mouth was observed in 123/415 (29.64%) patients in Group-A and 101/415 (24.34%) in Group-B (p-value 0.085), while constipation was observed in 41/415 (9.88%) patients in Group-A and 21/415(5.96%) patients in Group B. (p-value 0.000)

Conclusion: Solifenacin succinate (5mg) had significantly higher occurrence of constipation as compared to Tolterodine (4mg) while occurrence of dry mouth was also higher but not significant. These results showed that difference in side effects between Tolterodine and Solifenacin succinate in patients with urinary incontinence.

Key Words: Anti muscarinic, Solifenacin, Tolterodine, Overactive bladder, Dry Mouth, Constipation

INTRODUCTION

Urinary incontinence has been defined by the International Continence Society as “the complaint of any involuntary leakage of urine”.¹ The prevalence of urinary incontinence has been estimated as 13.1% in women and 5.4% in men in a recent population-based survey conducted across 5 countries.² Overactive bladder (OAB) is a symptom complex characterized by urinary urgency, which in turn drives the symptoms of frequency and nocturia with or without urgency incontinence. Epidemiological studies have estimated the prevalence of OAB to be 14%–16% after the age of 40 years and prevalence increases inexorably with age for both men and women.² It

is estimated that one third of OAB patients have urgency incontinence. The presence of urgency incontinence confers significant morbidity above and beyond that of OAB sufferers who are continent.³

Solifenacin and darfenacine are two new agents for OAB which have strong affinity for M3 receptors so comparable efficacy with lower side effects as compared to other anti-cholinergic agents. STAR trial comparing efficacy of Tolterodine with Solifenacin in OAB by Chapel and colleagues showed greater efficacy with mild to moderate side effects in both groups.^{4,5} HO Chang TC conducted study comparing the

Solifenacin and Tolteridine, equal efficacy in reducing the number of micturation (-2.56 ± 3.31 vs -2.44 ± 4.56 , $p=0.58$) with no major difference in quality of life. Incidence of dry mouth (18% vs 8.3%, $p=0.31$) and constipation (12.8% vs 2.8%, $p=0.20$) was not significantly different.⁶

The rationale of this study is to see the side effects of Solifenacin and Tolteridine as there is variability in side effects of Tolteridine and Solifenacin succinate in literature. In developing countries like Pakistan where basic health care is out of reach of common man a problem like urinary incontinence is largely overlooked and those who seek medical help remain non-compliant due to side effect if drug prescribed. Therefore, a study is required to choose a drug with lesser side effects to cope with the problem that make a woman's religious, marital and social life miserable and poses economic burden on family.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Dry Mouth: Abnormal reduction of saliva due to medication.

Constipation: Having a bowel movement fewer than three times per week.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This randomized controlled trial was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology THQ Hospital, Sadiqabad from March 2017 to September 2017. Total 830 patients having complaint of urinary incontinence, patients having complaints of nocturia, patients having complaints of frequency (The number of times a woman voids during her waking hours. Normally it is between 4-7 voids per day) were selected.

Patients with urinary tract infection (on urine complete examination), patients with fistula (History of continuous dribbling of urine), pregnancy, uterovaginal prolapse, patients with diabetes ($BSF > 126$ mg/dl and $BSR > 200$ mg/dl) were excluded from the study.

Patients were randomly divided (using lottery method) in both study groups. Group-A patients were treated with Solifenacin Succinate (5mg) and Tolteridine (4mg) in Group-B patients. Side

effects i.e constipation and dry mouth (as per operational definitions) were noted after 3 months post treatment.

Data was analyzed by using SPSS version 16. Mean and SD was calculated for numerical data. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical data.

RESULTS

Mean age of the patients was 58.34 ± 12.54 years mean age was 57.34 ± 11.33 years in Group-A patients and 55.44 ± 11.42 years in Group-B patients. When frequency of side effects were compared dry mouth was observed in 123 (29.64%) Group-A patients vs 101 (24.34%) in Group-B patients. (P value 0.085) (Table 1) When frequency of constipation were compared 41 (9.88%) patients in Group-A and 21 (5.96%) in Group-B patients had this complaint. This difference in both treatment groups was statistically significant. (p -value=0.000) (Table 2)

Table 1: Frequency of Dry Mouth In Treatment Groups

Side Effects	Group-A Solifenacin Succinate	Group-B Tolteridine	P value
YES	123 (29.64%)	101 (24.34%)	0.085
NO	292 (70.36%)	314 (75.66%)	
TOTAL	415	415	

Table-2: Frequency of Constipation in Treatment Groups

Side Effects	Group-A Solifenacin Succinate	Group-B Tolteridine	P value
YES	41 (9.88%)	21 (5.06%)	0.008
NO	374 (90.12%)	394 (94.93%)	
TOTAL	415	415	

DISCUSSION

Urinary incontinence is a major problem identified in women all over the world which affects their quality of life. This dilemma is commonest around the age of perimenopause and gradually worsens in old age.⁷

Antimuscarinics are established first line treatment options for overactive bladder. Therefore search of ideal antimuscarinic is going

on which effectively relief the symptoms of patient without increasing the side effects and easy dose adjustment.⁸ As the number of antimuscarinic are increasing, number of double blind randomized controlled are pitching one against other to show efficacy and tolerability of these agents Despite good efficacy antimuscrainic have significant side effects and compliance with treatment is at best average.⁹

Since the advent of solifenacin succinate 2005 numbers of trials are coming to compare with tolterodine regarding efficacy, and tolerability.¹⁰

The therapeutic profile however may differ because antimuscarinics have differing profiles of receptor interaction on the five subtypes of muscarinic receptor that represent targets for OAB treatments.¹¹ The major difference in efficacy and tolerability of different drugs is due to varied tissue absorption in peripheral tissue and selective action on bladder smooth muscle. In our study frequency of dry mouth was 29.64% in Solifenacin vs 24.34% in tolterodine (p-value=0.085) patients .C.R. Chapple in STAR trial compared solifenacin- and tolterodine ER and analysis of adverse events showed dry mouth in 30% of the patients who were given solifenacin and 24% in tolterodine group .⁴ In this study constipation was observed in 6.4% in solifenacin- and 2.5% in tolterodine group . In our study frequency of constipation was 9.88% in solifenacin treated patients versus (5.96%) in tolterodine treated group (p-value=0.000) The results are also comparable to another study by Chapple C.¹²

CONCLUSION

Solifenacin Succinate (5mg) had significantly higher occurrence of side effects than Tolterodine (4mg) in patients with urinary incontinence.

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